

COMPASSIONATE CARE

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PART 1: ALLOWING VISITATION

A. Ethical and Practical Question

Could and should visitation for COVID-19 patients be allowed?

B. Scenarios

1. A 24-year-old gentleman with autism who is ADL independent and diagnosed with Category 2 COVID. He appears to be anxious and restless in the low-risk quarantine centre. His primary caregiver is his mother, 50 years old with no comorbidities, requests visitation to help him manage his distress.
2. A 60-year-old lady with underlying advanced hepatocellular carcinoma and is diagnosed with Category 5 COVID-19. The multidisciplinary team deems her prognosis as palliative. Her husband, who is 64 years old with underlying ischemic heart disease and diabetes, requests visitation.
3. A 40-year-old gentleman has passed away due to COVID-19. His wife, a 39-year-old old lady who is physically healthy, is requesting to pay her last respects in the mortuary.

C. Background

1. Visitation to an ill person is an act of care and connection for both the patient and the loved ones. In addition, visiting a sick person could alleviate distress and anxiety on the respective parties, thus improves the treatment experience.
2. However, in highly contagious illnesses like COVID-19, unregulated visitations are counter-productive to infection control and public health measures. This has resulted in patients being nursed in isolation without visitation, including critically ill or dying patients.
3. Despite the utilitarian intention, such actions may be distressing to patients and carers, leading to poor treatment outcomes. Furthermore, regarding dying patients, being isolated can complicate grief in survivors and incur moral injury on the treating team.

D. Ethical Considerations and Justification

1. The stakeholders in this context are the patient, individuals who care for the person, and the treating team.

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2. Achieving visitation is the point of balance between *non-maleficence* (infection control) and *beneficence* (psychological support) along with subsidiary values of justice for all and the autonomy of the stakeholders. In other words, any action in this context should act in favour of the patient's health outcomes without over-burdening, provoking anxiety, risking the healthcare service, or public health interest.
3. It must be noteworthy that these recommendations are in line with the Standard 6: Patient and Family Rights of the Malaysian Society for Quality in Health 5th Edition of Hospital Accreditation Standards.

E. Recommendations

1. These recommendations are subjected to interpretation and implementation in individual healthcare facility and have to consider the resources available and the best interests of the population they serve.
2. Each healthcare facility has to develop and regularly update the resource and culturally appropriate "Visitation and Communication Policy".
 - a. Policies need to be developed and reviewed collaboratively by local stakeholders, including clinicians, support staff, managers, people (and their caregivers) with lived experience of COVID-19, and community members.
 - b. The policy should be a living document that guides and be guided by practice.
 - c. The policy may be accessible through the facility's patient information centre, posters, QR code, website, social media platforms, and other media deemed acceptable.
 - d. Language of the policy should be concise, clear, and friendly. Authoritarian and paternalistic language should be discouraged. An authorised interpreter or translation should be sought in the event of a language barrier.
 - e. The contents of the policy should cover the rationale of explaining why visitation is generally limited, the situations and processes of obtaining visitation.
 - f. Good practice would be to provide a copy of the policy to the patient and caregivers upon admission.
 - g. Pathway for end-users to address further questions either by telephone or e-mail should be included.
3. Decision makers in each unit and shift should be identified, trained and supported especially in event of grievances.
4. Communication of patients to their carers should be a universal requirement:
 - a. The most basic communication access for patients to the outside world, e.g. telephone access, in each ward or facility for daily use by non-seriously ill COVID-19 patients, may be made available. An example of innovative and personalised communication is using plexiglass booths with telephones on either side for patients and visitors.

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- b. Ethical usage of own telecommunication devices by patients should be encouraged.
 - c. With the availability of resources, local managers should ensure good telecommunication coverage in admitting facilities to support video and telephone calls. Example: Installation of a wireless network in isolation wards and upgrading of coverage by local telecommunications companies.
 - d. In more resource-intensive set-ups like high-dependency and intensive care units, designated visitor booths may be set up in clean zones with mobile video consoles such as tablets where-in visitors can view and communicate with the patient by the bedside through video telecommunications:
 - i. Scheduled communication is the key in balancing the need for communication without disrupting clinical work.
 - ii. For patients who cannot communicate, staff should be trained to support communication from both ends.
5. Visitation of COVID-19 patients, if considered, has to be a deliberate and resource-informed decision:
- a. Ideally, there should be only one visitor who can use the PPE without difficulty for a visitation that lasts less than 15 minutes.
 - b. Overall need of stakeholders (patient, caregiver,s and treating team) vs. clinical severity or demographic should guide visitation.
 - c. Individuals who may be considered visitation (non-exhaustive list):
 - i. Critically ill patient
 - ii. Palliative patient
 - iii. Individual with special needs*
 - iv. Younger persons (< 18 years of age)*
 - v. Individual with marked psychological distress**
 - vi. Person in labour

* may allow admission with one low-risk caregiver with necessary informed consent and safeguard.

** input from Psychiatrist can be sought by the decision-maker in allowing visitation

- d. Visitation may be requested by a patient, caregiver (friend or family), or the treating team.
- e. Information regarding request and process of visitation should be made known to patients and caregivers in the public domain and given during admission.
- f. Transparent and equitable visitation application system has to be maintained by the healthcare facility.
- g. The decision to accept visitor/s in a patient with capacity is first the patient and then the decision-maker in a treating team.
- h. Equitable use of resources, especially PPE and staff availability, should also be taken into consideration. In the event of limitation of PPE, in-person visitation may be converted to phone or video communication.
- i. The visitor of a patient with COVID-19 should be able to comprehend necessary infection control precautions. This includes the use of personal protective equipment (PPE) and should not be at elevated risk for COVID-19 vs general population:

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- i. The treating team's decision-maker should determine the visitor's eligibility fairly and equitably, including obtaining the visitor's background medical and social history (see 6 (c)).
 - ii. Visitation duration should be time-limited (less than 15 minutes) and supervised.
 - iii. The number of visitors is ideally limited and decided by the local treating team's visitation policy.
 - iv. Informed consent of visitation to the visitor in undertaking risks of visitation and contingency management.
 - j. Feedback post-visitation may be obtained to guide future service improvement.
6. Different standards of regulations should be employed regarding the visitation of non-COVID-19 and COVID-19 wards.
- a. Visitation policies to non-COVID-19 wards need to consider the patient's clinical condition (e.g., terminally ill, young person who is ill), ward environment, caregiving needs (e.g., autistic individuals), and the overall pandemic climate. Wards with young people and individuals with intellectual impairment should require less restrictive and more flexible policies.
 - b. These policies need to be incorporated into unit or department operational procedures in responding to the pandemic.
 - c. Visitors who are in the high-risk group for severe COVID-19, recent exposure to COVID-19 or symptomatic of COVID-19 should be prohibited from visiting or providing caregiving.
 - d. Visitors are expected to comply with infection control practices, including regular hand hygiene, masking, and person-time limited visitation (e.g., one visitor per patient for less than 15 minutes).
 - e. Ideally, a visitor-caregiver bubble (minimal and similar people with an established geosocial movement pattern) has to be maintained, which can be contained in the event of COVID-19 spread. A log of visitors has to be maintained as part of the nursing process for each patient.
 - f. Policy reviews concerning non-COVID-19 wards require flexibility, with close reference to the latest COVID-19 pandemic status in the local community, of which visitation may be allowed or halted temporarily.
 - g. Testing pathways would also need to be established and communicated to the visitors in the event of a spread of COVID-19 infection in the ward.

PART 2: EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION

A. Practical Question

How should we communicate with patients and families during COVID-19?

B. Scenarios

1. A 32-year-old man diagnosed with COVID-19 stage 3 was seen trying to force open locked doors in the ward to abscond. When he failed to do so, he was seen crying softly in a dark corner. Further questioning revealed that his young children were at home alone, and he was unsure when he would be discharged.
2. A 17-year-old girl had completed treatment in the ward for her COVID-19 diagnosis and was planned for discharge. However, the family was unwilling to accept her home as they were worried that she would spread the illness to the whole family.
3. A 23-year-old woman had just passed away due to complications of COVID-19. The treatment team was anxious to break the news to the husband. He had a history of being emotionally volatile and shouting at hospital personnel when his wife was admitted to the ward.

C. Background

1. Anxiety often arises during periods of uncertainty when the sense of control over one's life is disrupted. Uncertainty about the impact and consequences of the illness, the details and length of their admission and quarantine, and the ongoing events and stressors at home may cause high stress and anxiety levels in patients and their families.
2. Unresolved stress and anxiety may cause disruptive psychological issues such as extreme fear, anger, sadness or guilt, panic attacks, insomnia, and suicidal thoughts or behaviour. Patients may become uncooperative, and in some cases, abscond from their areas of quarantine. Family members may also have many uncertainties about the illness, which may lead to stigmatising behaviour towards their discharged family members, such as fearful behaviour, avoidance, and isolation of recovered patients.
3. Importantly, we may cope better after receiving a bad outcome when compared to being left uncertain with no information. Thus, in offering compassionate care to patients, proper communication between health providers and the patient and their families is essential to reduce uncertainty and anxiety.

D. Recommendations

1. Communication with patients and family members should optimally be done during these specific occasions:
 - a. Prior to and during the screening process.
 - b. Once the positive result is confirmed, i.e. breaking bad news.
 - c. Daily during the quarantine/hospital stay.
 - d. When there is a change in clinical status, e.g. from stage 2 to stage 3.
 - e. Prior to discharge.

2. The content of the communication should aim to:
 - a. Provide adequate and continuous medical education to patients by the treating team. Topics may include information about COVID-19, duration of illness and infectivity, possible long-term sequelae, prognosis, treatment options and progress, and guidelines on how to reduce the risk of infection and transmission.

 - b. Provide adequate and up-to-date information to patients about their quarantine or hospital stay, including the expected length of stay and the expected discharge date.

 - c. Provide adequate medical education to the family members and caregivers. The goal is to reduce anxiety and stigmatising behaviour towards patients discharged from wards or quarantine centres.

3. The following are some strategies to communicate effectively:
 - a. Communication should be honest while remaining empathetic.
 - b. Effective non-verbal communication techniques should be used.
 - c. Communication should be using simple, short, and clear language without jargon.
 - d. Metaphors or abstract examples should be avoided as they may cause confusion and misunderstanding.
 - e. Important points may need to be repeated, and clarifications and questions should be allowed.
 - f. Whenever possible, translators should be provided to those having difficulty understanding the language of communication.

4. There are various communication techniques available to guide clinicians in achieving effective and empathetic communication. Some examples of these techniques include:
 - a. The SPIKES Protocol – for breaking bad news ([Chapter 2](#))
 - b. The EVE Protocol – for empathetic listening and emotional validation ([Appendix A](#))
 - c. The BUSTER Protocol – for challenging conversations ([Appendix A](#))
 - d. The RED-MAP Approach ([Appendix A](#))

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5. While the ward staff can do daily updates and communications, more critical and challenging communications should optimally be conducted by a senior member of the team. To add the link to Appendix
6. Possible methods of delivery are booklets, pamphlets, short PA system announcements, posters, banners, infographics, and videos delivered through messaging apps or QR codes, telephone calls, video conferencing sessions, and if necessary, short face-to-face engagements with proper precautions and PPEs.
7. Communication aids such as booklets, pamphlets, QR codes, or messaging apps may be beneficial for family members.
8. Some challenges may occur during communication with patients while using Personal Protective Equipment (PPE). Some techniques to overcome this may include:
 - a. Medical staff introducing themselves clearly before every encounter to aid recognition which is impaired by the lack of visual clues.
 - b. Using printed names, photographs, or attaching short biographies to PPEs to increase humanization.
 - c. Pronouncing words clearly, enunciating slowly, and speaking at a higher volume, to counteract the impeding effects of the face mask and shield.
9. Patients should be equipped with relaxation techniques, distraction techniques, and other skills to help them regain their sense of control. Examples of techniques include breathing exercise, progressive muscle relaxation (PMR), grounding technique, and focusing on elements within their control.
10. The Mental Health and Psychosocial Services (MHPSS) and their contact details should be offered.

PART 3: PSYCHOLOGICAL SUPPORT FOR END-OF-LIFE CARE

A. Practical Question

How could we support the healthcare givers, caregivers, and patients better?

B. Scenarios

1. A 29-year-old female staff nurse working in the COVID-19 ICU for the past three months complained of feeling anxious easily and associated with irritability, poor sleep, palpitations, and tremors. She has called for five emergency leaves over the past two weeks. Upon probing, she told her supervisor that she did not want to work in the COVID ward anymore. She found herself too tired to continue working.
2. The wife of a 50-year-old gentleman who was just intubated less than 24 hours ago for COVID-19 has been calling the ward every hour to ask about her husband's progress. She requested to visit her husband, fearing that this would be the last time for her to meet him. She has been crying while talking over the phone.

C. Background

1. The death rate worldwide is expected to rise significantly since the emergence of the unprecedented event of pandemic COVID-19. In the UK, the high rate of death was reported at 26% from a total of 20 133 patients positive to COVID-19 who required hospitalisation. The total accumulative reported deaths in Malaysia is 4069 cases which are 0.61% of the total cases of 667 876 on 15th June 2021, reported by Crisis Preparedness and Response Centre (CPRC), Ministry of Health, Malaysia.
2. Rapid disease progression, a change in compassionate care delivery during the pandemic, and limitation of health care resources, may shift end-of-life care management and decisions. These inevitably would lead to more complicated psychological issues, including prolonged grief and bereavement among the healthcare workers, patients, and caregivers.

D. Ethical Considerations and Justifications

1. Psychological distress, including major mental health diagnoses such as depression, anxiety, and delirium, may compromise a patient's autonomy to make informed decisions regarding his medical treatment and management, including end-of-life decisions.

2. During pandemic COVID-19, the prevalence of psychological distress is even higher in comparison to during non-pandemic situations. Shared decision-making should be made between the treating team and main caregivers based on the patient's best interest and ensure optimal quality of life.

E. Recommendations

1. Healthcare Workers

- a. Multidisciplinary team consensus.
- b. To ensure a uniform and consistent statement/s being delivered to the patients and caregivers.
 - i. To reduce the burden of moral distress among the healthcare workers.
 - ii. To avoid confusion and maintain trusting relationship with patients and caregivers. form consensus on treatment decisions
- c. Training of communication skills (e.g. breaking bad news) and grief.
- d. Enabling grief support for healthcare workers (e.g. individual or group formats).

2. Caregivers

- a. Caregivers are encouraged to be part of end-of-life conversations, of which emphatic and consistent information on current medical management and plan with regular updates on patient progression are provided.
- b. To increase awareness of the psychological issues among caregivers that may arise in end-of-life situations and encourage help-seeking behaviour i.e. recognising and managing grief, anxiety, depression etc.
- c. To address the challenges during conversations with patients due to respiratory symptoms such as breathlessness, respiratory support machines, and the possibility of rapid cognitive deterioration, including delirium.
- d. To provide psychological support to the caregivers after the patient has passed away (to address the funerals issues e.g. unable to carry out the usual religious/cultural rituals).
- e. To recognise and address the spiritual needs of caregivers.

3. Patients

- a. To allow early end-of-life conversations with vulnerable patients such as patients with multiple comorbidities, elderly and rapid disease progression. This may include discussions about future treatment decisions and practical issues at home.
- b. To provide an early assessment and intervention for psychological distress or major mental health issues e.g. grief, loneliness, isolation, anxiety, depression etc.

PART 4: CHAPLAINCY AND SPIRITUAL CARE SERVICES

A. Practical Question

How could chaplaincy/ spiritual care services be delivered during the pandemic COVID-19?

B. Scenarios

1. A 60-year-old Muslim Malay gentleman with underlying hypertension and diabetes was diagnosed with COVID-19 category 3 requested for an Ustaz to attend to him prior to intubation (if needed/ if his condition deteriorated) as he has ‘some favour’ he must request from, fearing that he won’t be able to ‘make it’ this time.
2. A 35-year-old, Christian Chinese lady with no underlying medical illness and was diagnosed with COVID-19 category 2 has requested to see her pastor to help her with the anxiety feelings she has been experiencing since receiving a call from the health district office about her close contact contact to a positive case.

C. Background

1. The World Health Organization (WHO) has included chaplaincy care as one of the services integrated into palliative care. However, there are no formal chaplaincy services in health care facilities in the Ministry of Health (MOH) to date.
2. Nevertheless, the ministry already launched guidelines for *Hospital Mesra Ibadah* (MIH), in which the services are currently available, focusing specifically on Muslims to fulfill their religious duty.

D. Definition

1. The European Association of Palliative Care (EAPC) defined spirituality as ‘the dynamic dimension of human life that relates to the way persons (individual and community) experiences, express and/or seek meaning purpose and transcendence and the way they connect to the moment, to self, to others, to nature, to the significant and/or the sacred.’ Spiritual care is conceived as;

“That care which recognizes and responds to the needs of the human spirit when faced with trauma, ill health or sadness and can include the need for meaning, for self-worth, to express oneself, for faith support, perhaps for rites or prayer or sacrament or simply for a sensitive listener.”

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2. The role of chaplaincy care is to address the needs for spirituality, religiosity, bereavement process for the healthcare providers, patients, and their caregivers. A good understanding of spirituality and the different perspectives or needs of the patients, caregivers, and healthcare workers is important to ensure better well-being and improve the quality of life. The wide-range, various chaplaincy services are even more critical in this multi-religion, multicultural country.
3. During this COVID-19 pandemic, restriction for visitation even during the last moments of life, including the funeral process, limits the usual rituals conducted by the family members in accordance with specific religious and cultural practices. This inevitably may lead to a more complex bereavement process not only for the caregivers, but also the healthcare workers. Thus, chaplaincy care services may alleviate the spiritual pain and distress by helping stakeholders go through the bereavement process in a more adaptive way.

E. Ethical Considerations and Justifications

1. To ensure the patient's autonomy is not being compromised as spirituality is part of holistic medical care without imposing any judgment on the patient's spiritual or religious practice or preference.
2. To ensure any spiritual or religious practice requested does no harm and is beneficial during the medical treatment.

F. Principles

1. The chaplaincy/ spiritual services shall be inclusive to all religious and spiritual beliefs given the diverse population of Malaysia.
2. The chaplaincy/ spiritual services are part of the integrated care and multidisciplinary team of the patient, caregiver/s and healthcare professionals.
3. The chaplaincy/ spiritual services are delivered as person-centered care/ family-centered care according to the best practices by the federal and state laws, regulations, and rules.
4. The chaplaincy/ spiritual services shall adhere to the ethical principles to guide decision-making and professional behavior.
5. The chaplaincy/ spiritual services shall be delivered by a person who has received the required training to ensure best practices in promoting patient well-being.

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6. The chaplaincy/ spiritual services shall be delivered/ provided with strict adherence to the Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) during the pandemic COVID-19 at all times.

G. The Chaplaincy/Spiritual Care Teams

1. General members: Healthcare workers from various levels, such as consultants/specialists/ trainees/medical officers/nurses, who have undergone required basic training to provide spiritual/pastoral care.
2. Specialized members:
 - a. Palliative care physicians/psychiatrists/clinical psychologists/counsellors/trainees who have undergone specific training in spiritual care preferably palliative or end-of-life care, including grief work.
 - b. Appointed religious or spiritual representative hospital/ other acknowledged association (*those requested by caregivers may be considered), preferably with psychology/counselling background.
3. The team members must understand and agreed to adhere to the restrictions or guidelines during this pandemic COVID-19 at all times.
4. It is encouraged to use available technology, for example, telephone or video call, to minimize any risk during this pandemic COVID-19 without compromising the benefits of chaplaincy/ spiritual care.
5. The spiritual care must adhere to the privacy and confidentiality issues between the provider and the receiver of the chaplaincy/spiritual care services.
 - a. People who receive care have the right to information confidential between the spiritual care provider and themselves. If information is to be shared with the multidisciplinary team for case management purposes, the provider should inform the patient before communication.
 - b. However, it must be noted that the provider may breach confidentiality if they obtain information that indicates a compromised safety of the patient and/or others. Suicidal risk is one such situation.
6. Spiritual care is part of a care plan. Therefore, it has to be documented and filed. Relevant and agreed information can also be documented in the case notes.
7. The service/s provided should emphasize person-centred care in decision-making and advance care planning.
8. A suitable space such as a chaplaincy unit/a private room should be available for the chaplaincy/spiritual care services.
9. The chaplaincy/spiritual care services may be invited during the regular multidisciplinary team meeting or as needed.

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- a. If there are urgent issues during spiritual care, the chaplain should consider informing the nurses/the doctor for an urgent feedback/ meeting.

H. Steps for Chaplaincy/Spiritual Care Services

1. Offer “Spiritual Care” services to both patients and caregivers in both non-COVID-19 and suspected/confirmed COVID-19 cases.
 - a. Checklist during admission. It is important to offer at the early point of admission as some of the COVID-19 patients may deteriorate rapidly ([Appendix B](#)).
 - b. Patients should be supported if they have any last wishes in the event of a deterioration or before intubation. This wish should be documented clearly and, if suitable, to deliver the information to the caregiver/s too.
 - c. To document any preferred/ required ritual, prayer or chanting according to the beliefs/culture as requested by the patient/caregiver/s, especially when clinical condition deteriorates.
 - d. Information on the chaplaincy/spiritual care services should be made available on the hospital’s official website or through exhibited posters in the ward.
2. Spiritual Needs Assessment can be done using The HOPE Questions ([Appendix C](#)). A Formal Spiritual Assessment in a Medical Interview could be conducted to assess specific individual needs in regard to religious, spiritual, and cultural domains.
 - a. Patients, either non-COVID-19 or suspected/confirmed COVID-19, may voluntarily request the chaplaincy/ spiritual services as needed.
 - b. Patients/ caregivers may be referred to the chaplaincy/ spiritual services by the healthcare professional if agreed by the patients/ caregivers at any time during the admission/ treatment.
3. To consider spiritual care delivery per local policy during the COVID-19 pandemic:
 - a. A referral and documentation should be made accordingly.
 - b. To liaise with the infection control team to ensure spiritual care can be delivered optimally without compromising the local infection control policy, including the need to wear PPE.
 - c. To identify if an urgent response is required. A specific date and time should be arranged accordingly.
 - d. To identify the specific person/ organization who will deliver the spiritual care.
 - e. To identify the most suitable means for the delivery of spiritual care.
 - i. Is face-to-face (by following the current consultation policy during COVID-19 pandemic) spiritual care feasible, especially for the non-COVID-19 patients?
 - ii. Is telephone/ virtual consultation possible?
4. To discuss opportunities for future memorialization.

5. To offer continuity of chaplaincy/ spiritual care services to the caregiver/s or healthcare workers after the patient passed away.

I. Spiritual/ Chaplaincy Care Services on Special Population

1. Healthcare workers (HCWs)
 - a. Spiritual/ religious/ bereavement issues among the healthcare workers may be addressed from time to time. A pathway for referral either from self or other colleagues such as the immediate supervisor/ team leader should be made available in all hospitals.
2. Children and adolescents
 - a. Spiritual and religious rights among the children are explicitly documented in the UN Convention on The Rights of the Children.
 - b. The need for chaplaincy/spiritual care could be discussed
 - i. With the main caregiver;
 - ii. During the consultation/clinical assessment when the healthcare professional believed the chaplaincy/ spiritual care and intervention might be beneficial for the child/adolescent;
 - iii. If requested by the child/adolescent (the main caregiver should be informed, and consent given); or
 - iv. If requested by the caregiver/s for the child/adolescent.
3. End-of-life/ ICU patient
 - a. An early discussion regarding any spiritual/religious needs should be carried out during the admission, given that the clinical condition in a COVID-19 patient may deteriorate rapidly.
 - b. Any ritual/ prayer/chanting shall be carried out appropriately as documented or requested by the patient/caregiver/s.
 - c. If there is no such documentation, the respective chaplaincy/spiritual personnel may deliver any ritual/ prayer/chanting where appropriate with consent.
4. Caretakers of COVID-19 patient
 - a. The caretaker/s of the patient with COVID-19 patient may request chaplaincy/spiritual care services during the admission and may wish to continue with the services after discharge or after the patient had passed away.
 - b. Grief and bereavement service/s may be offered if appropriate or if required.
 - c. Follow-up may be conducted by the respective hospital's Mental Health and Psychosocial Support team (if available).

PART 5: OTHER PSYCHOLOGICAL ISSUES

What are other psychological issues that have to be considered to ensure compassionate care?

The authors opine that providing compassionate care in difficult situations could only be optimal when the psychological well-being of the relevant stakeholders: patients, caregivers, treatment providers and healthcare managers is taken care of. Within the Ministry of Health, the Mental Health & Psychosocial Support framework provides this service and can be referenced.

Issues which are encouraged to be addressed are:

1. Awareness of psychological issues that may arise in such situations as burnout and grief.
2. Self-care
3. Management of boredom in patients

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APPENDIX A: OTHER COMMUNICATION TOOLS

THE EVE PROTOCOL

To be used in emotionally charged situations, to aid empathetic listening and emotional validation.

E – Explore the Emotion

How does this make you feel?

I can see that you look angry when talking about what happened.

I have had patients who feel sad in this situation. What about you?

V – Validate the Emotion

I am not surprised that you feel that way.

Most people would feel angry too.

I have had many patients who felt that way too.

E – Empathetic Response

I am sorry this happened to you.

That must have been very difficult.

I hear what you are saying. It was obviously very upsetting.

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The BUSTER Protocol

To be used during challenging conversations, to facilitate communication and validate emotions.

B - Be Prepared

Choose an appropriate place and time for the conversation.

Expect emotions from the patient.

Be aware of your own emotions and prepare to self-regulate.

U - Use Non-Judgmental Listening

Use good non-verbal communication and eye contact.

Listen without interrupting, clarify, and paraphrase.

CHAPTER 4: COMPASSIONATE CARE
Best Practice in Clinical Ethics and Compassionate Care during COVID-19 Crisis

*It is not about you or your values.
Put your agenda aside until later.
Avoid trying to make things better – It's not that bad.*

S - Six Second Rule

*When you start to feel strong emotions, wait for six seconds before reacting.
Avoid blaming or being defensive – Well, if you came in for treatment earlier, things would not be so bad!*

T - “Tell Me More” Statements

*What happened after that?
Can you tell me more?*

E - Empathize and Validate

*This is not an easy situation, is it?
This is very stressful, isn't it?
It must be difficult for you.*

R - Respond with a Wish Statement

*I wish we had better news to tell you.
I wish we had better treatment options.
I wish things were different for you.*

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The RED-MAP Approach

Used during conversations with patients about their medical condition, to align and manage expectations, treatment goals.

R - Ready

Adequately plan conversations, to ensure so everyone is prepared, and the right people are involved.

Hello, Mr Ali? My name is..., I am a (your title).

Can we schedule time to talk about your treatment? Who else do you want to be around during the conversation?

CHAPTER 4: COMPASSIONATE CARE
Best Practice in Clinical Ethics and Compassionate Care during COVID-19 Crisis

Who should we talk to if you are more unwell or not able to make decisions about treatment plans?

E - Expect

Find out about their understanding and expectations about the illness. Allow questions and explore worries.

*What do you understand about this illness?
Do you have any questions about what is happening?*

D - Diagnosis

Share information suitable to their current understanding and background. Use short sentences with pauses. Use simple language. Acknowledge and share uncertainty. Be empathetic.

*I'm afraid you are seriously unwell.
We don't know exactly what will happen or when, but we can plan for what to do if...
We hope you will improve with..., but I am worried about...*

M - Matters

Pause to let them take in the information. Find out what is important to them.

*Is there anything we should know about how you would like to be cared for if you became very unwell?
Anything you do not want/wish to avoid?*

A - Actions

Talk about realistic, available options for treatment and care. Be clear about what will not work or help.

*What we can do to help is...
This does not work/help.*

P - Plan

Clearly record care plans and DNR decisions if applicable.

Let's make a plan for your treatment options.

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APPENDIX B: FLOWCHART OF CHAPLAINCY & SPIRITUAL CARE (HOSPITAL SERVICES) DURING PANDEMIC COVID-19 OUTBREAK

APPENDIX C: THE HOPE QUESTIONS FOR A FORMAL SPIRITUAL ASSESSMENT IN A MEDICAL INTERVIEW

H: Sources of hope, meaning, comfort, strength, peace, love and connection

O: Organized religion

P: Personal spirituality and practices

E: Effects on medical care and end-of-life issues

Examples of Questions for the HOPE Approach to Spiritual Assessment

H: Sources of hope, meaning, comfort, strength, peace, love and connection

- We have been discussing your support systems. I was wondering, what is there in your life that gives you internal support?
- What are your sources of hope, strength, comfort and peace?
- What do you hold on to during difficult times?
- What sustains you and keeps you going?
- For some people, their religious or spiritual beliefs act as a source of comfort and strength in dealing with life's ups and downs; is this true for you?
- If the answer is “Yes,” go on to O and P questions.
- If the answer is “No,” ask: Was it ever? If the answer is “Yes,” ask: What changed?

O: Organized religion

- Do you consider yourself part of an organized religion?
- How important is this to you?
- What aspects of your religion are helpful and not so helpful to you?
- Are you part of a religious or spiritual community? Does it help you? How?

P: Personal spirituality/ practices

- Do you have personal spiritual beliefs that are independent of organized religion? What are they?
- Do you believe in God? What kind of relationship do you have with God?
- What aspects of your spirituality or spiritual practices do you find most helpful to you personally? (e.g., prayer, meditation, reading scripture, attending religious services, listening to music, hiking, communing with nature)

E: Effects on medical care and end-of-life issues

- Has being sick (or your current situation) affected your ability to do the things that usually help you spiritually? (Or affected your relationship with God?)
- As a doctor, is there anything that I can do to help you access the resources that usually help you?
- Are you worried about any conflicts between your beliefs and your medical situation/care/decisions?
- Would it be helpful for you to speak to a clinical chaplain/community spiritual leader?
- Are there any specific practices or restrictions I should know about in providing your medical care? (e.g., dietary restrictions, use of blood products)
- *If the patient is dying: How do your beliefs affect the kind of medical care you would like me to provide over the next few days/weeks/months?*